

Application of Semi-Quantitative Theory of Resonance for Comparative Study of the Reactivity of the Like Positions in Some Hydroxycoumarins in Electrophilic Substitution

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With the help of Bartell's equation the difference in resonance energy of the metastable intermediate states leading to substitutions (electrophilic) in positions 8 and 6 of 7-hydroxycoumarin, in positions 5 and 7 of 6-hydroxycoumarin and in positions 6 and 8 of 5-hydroxycoumarin have been calculated. On this basis it has been concluded that the position 8 should be more reactive than 6 in 7-hydroxycoumarin, position 5 should be more reactive than 7 in 6-hydroxycoumarin and positions 6 and 8 should have equal reactivity in 5-hydroxycoumarin in electrophilic substitution. These deductions have been compared with the experimental observations made in the literature.

In a previous communication¹, it was pointed out that the application of Bartell's equation² for resonance energy of a molecule (where RE is resonance energy of a molecule, $RE = \frac{1}{2} \beta (N_d - \sum p_{ij}^2)$ N_d is the number of double bonds in any individual bonds resonating structures, P_{ij} are the Pauling bond orders and β is the resonance integral in M.O. theory) the thermochemical value of which is 18 Kcal to electrophilic substitution in styrene leads to the conclusion contrary to the general notion that the *ortho* directing tendency in styrene should be more than the *para* directing tendency. The veracity of this deduction cannot be so easily verified experimentally in such type of compounds as the other factors such as steric hindrance, polar effects etc. hinders substitution in the *ortho* position.

Bartell's equation² is now applied to assess comparative reactivity of two similar positions in some hydroxycoumarins viz., positions 8 and 6 in 7-hydroxycoumarin, 5 and 7 in 6-hydroxycoumarin and 6 and 8 in 5-hydroxycoumarin in electrophilic substitution. The calculation of actual value of resonance energy of the intermediate states leading to substitution in these positions is not possible as it is difficult to compute and correlate the bonds of C and C with those of C and other hetero atoms like O, nevertheless the value of difference in resonance energy of the intermediate states having similar resonating forms can be calculated by the method worked out below.

Resonance energy of the metastable intermediate states in electrophilic substitution of hydroxycoumarins.

7-Hydroxycoumarin: The contributing structures of the intermediate state leading

1. Usgaonkar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, 35, 620.
2. Bartell, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 139.

to substitution in position 8 (state I) are

and leading to substitution in position 6 (state II) are

The corresponding Pauling bond orders calculated on the basis of these contributing structures are given in fig. 1 A and B respectively:

An inspection of the contributing structures of I and II show that except for those bond orders whose values are given in fig. 1 A and B respectively, the other aspects of the resonating structures in the two cases remain exactly the same. The value of N_d in case of both the intermediate states (I & II) is then obtained as $(2+x)$ where x , is added to the actual number of resonating carbon-carbon double bonds (which is 2 in both I & II), to account for the other π bonds in the resonating structures of the two intermediate states whose values are difficult to compute but they are same in both the cases. In the same manner

$$\sum p_{ij}^2 \text{ for the state I} = \{(3/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (3/5)^2 + y_1\}$$

$$\sum p_{ij}^2 \text{ for the state II} = \{(3/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (1/5)^2 + (4/5)^2 + y_2\}$$

where γ_i is added in both the cases to account for the sum of square of bond orders of those bonds of I and II whose values are not given in Fig. 1 A and B respectively as it is difficult to compute them but they are same in both I and II. RE of these intermediate states calculated by inserting the respective values of N_d and $\sum p_{ij}^2$ in the Bartell's equation and the difference in RE of the two are given in table I and discussed subsequently.

6-Hydroxycoumarin—The contributing structures of the intermediate state leading to substitution in position 5 (state I) are

and leading to substitution in position 7 (state II) are

The corresponding Pauling bond orders (p_{ij}) of I and II calculated on the basis of these contributing structures are given in fig. 2 A and B respectively

An inspection of the contributing structures of I and II leads to the conclusion similar to the one arrived before in case of 7-hydroxycoumarin. The values of N_d and p_{ij}^2

for these intermediate states may therefore be written as

$$N_d \text{ (for I and II)} = (3+x_a)$$

$$P_{ij}^a \text{ (for I)} = \left\{ (3/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (3/5)^2 + (3/5)^2 + (1/5)^2 + (4/5)^2 + y_a \right\}$$

$$P_{ij}^a \text{ (for II)} = \left\{ (3/5)^2 + (2/5)^2 + (1/5)^2 + (4/5)^2 + (1/5)^2 + (4/5)^2 + y_a \right\}$$

where x_a and y_a are added as corrections in the same sense as x_i and y_i are used in case of 7-hydroxycoumarin. The calculated values of RE for the two intermediate states with the help of the equation and the difference in RE of the two are given in table I and discussed subsequently.

6-Hydroxycoumarin.—The contributing structures of the intermediate state leading to substitution in position 6 (state I) are

and leading to substitution in position 8 (state II) are

The Pauling bond orders calculated on the basis of these contributing structures are given in Fig. 3 A and B respectively.

Fig. 3

An inspection of the resonating structures of I and II leads to the conclusion similar to that arrived in case of 7-hydroxy- and 6-hydroxycoumarins. The values of N_d and $\sum p_{ij}^a$ for these intermediate states may therefore be written as

$$N_d \text{ (for I and II)} = (2+x_3)$$

$$P_{ij}^a \text{ (for I)} = \left\{ (4/5)^a + (1/5)^a + (2/5)^a + (3/5)^a + y_3 \right\}$$

$$P_{ij}^a \text{ (for II)} = \left\{ (4/5)^a + (1/5)^a + (2/5)^a + (3/5)^a + y_3 \right\}$$

where x_3 and y_3 are added as corrections in same sense as x_1 and y_1 are used in case of 7-hydroxycoumarin. The calculated values of RE of the two intermediate states with the help of the equation are given in table I and discussed subsequently.

TABLE I

Coumarin	RE of the intermediate state I RE (I)	RE of the intermediate state II RE (II)	Difference in resonance energy* RE(I)-RE(II)
7-Hydroxy	$32/25\beta + 4/3\beta (x_1 - y_1)$	$16/15\beta + 4/3\beta (x_1 - y_1)$	3.84 Kcal
6-Hydroxy	$128/75\beta + 4/3\beta (x_2 - y_2)$	$112/75\beta + 4/3\beta (x_2 - y_2)$	3.84 Kcal
3-Hydroxy	$16/15\beta + 4/3\beta (x_3 - y_3)$	$16/15\beta + 4/3\beta (x_3 - y_3)$	0 Kcal

* $\beta = 18$ Kcal

DISCUSSION

The tabulated results (table I) show that the equation has enabled to bring clarity regarding the stability of the metastable intermediate states and thus has enabled to get an idea about the activation energy required for substitution in the two positions of the same coumarin.

7-Hydroxycoumarin: In case of this coumarin, according to the calculations (table I), the intermediate state leading to substitution in position 8 is stabilised by 3.84 Kcal of more RE in comparison with that leading to substitution in position 6. The activation energy is therefore low by 3.84 Kcal for substitution in position 8 than in position 6 and though this difference is not very high, the tendency for substitution in position 8 should be greater than that for substitution in position 6. It is interesting to note that the same conclusion was drawn by Rangaswami and Seshadri³ on the basis of classical theory of fixation of double bonds.

The deduction is in complete agreement with the observations made by Dharmatti et al⁴ in proton magnetic resonance study. Values of chemical shifts for the protons at

3. Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Proc., Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 14A, 547 see also R. C. Shah, (*Presidential address*), *Proc., 38th Indian Sci. Cong.* 1951, (II) 103; Thakor and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1947-48, 38.

4. Dharmatti, Govil, Kanchar, Khetrapal and Virmani, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1962, 56A, 71.

positions 6 and 8 (-5.23 & -5.18 p.p.m. respectively for 7-hydroxycoumarin and -5.34 & -5.18 p.p.m. respectively for 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin) distinctly show that the position 8 has got electron density slightly more than that of 6 and therefore the former should be more reactive than the latter in electrophilic substitutions. This is well supported by the experimental observations made in the literature. In the number of electrophilic reactions of 7-hydroxycoumarin and its 4-methyl derivative viz., Friedel and Craft's acylation^{2b,e}, Fries reaction^{3a,d}, Claisen transformation⁵, sulphination with thionyl chloride^{7a}, Pechmann condensation⁸ and many other reactions⁹ reported in the literature, the major product has always been 8-substituted derivative. 6-substituted derivative is obtained in few cases as minor product in negligible amounts. In cases where the position 8 is blocked in these coumarins, these reactions have taken place smoothly to give 6-substituted derivative.

Bromination^{10a} and nitration^{11a,b,e} reactions of 7-hydroxycoumarin and/or its 4-methyl derivative provide exceptions. In these reactions a mixture of 6- and 8-substituted derivatives are obtained in more or less equal amounts^a. The cause for this may be attributed to the steric and polar effects (+ve character) of -O- in the heterocyclic ring which hinders the approach of the electrophiles to the position 8 to some extent. It is felt in these particular cases to an appreciable extent because the electrophiles Br⁺ and N⁺O₂ ions are bulky and more +ve in character in comparison to the electrophiles like C⁺OMe. The position 6 is therefore simultaneously attacked by these electrophiles. The bulkier and more +ve the electrophile, less should be its accessibility to the position 8 and S⁺O₃H ion is bulkier and more +ve in character than Br⁺ and N⁺O₂ ions and accordingly sulphonation of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has been reported to furnish the 6-sulphonic acid of the coumarin as major product¹². The relative magnitude of the +ve character of the electrophiles viz., S⁺O₃H, N⁺O₂, Br⁺, C⁺OMe etc. referred above is judged from the

*Controversy exists regarding the product reported in nitration of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. Earlier authors^{11a,b} have reported the formation of 8-nitro derivative (m.p. 256°) while the latter authors^{11c} have reported the formation of 6-nitro isomer (m.p. 253°). A.R. Naik^{11c} in his thesis has mentioned to have obtained a crude nitro product (m.p. 229-30°) from which he isolated the 6-nitro isomer, the mixed m.p. of which with the authentic 8-nitro isomer was 229-30°. This suggests that in nitration a mixture of 6- and 8-nitro isomers are formed in nearly equal amounts.

5. (a) Limaye, *Ber.*, 1932, 63B, 375; (b) *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1934, 67B, 12; (c) Limaye *et al.*, *Researches*, 1936, 20; *ibid.*, 1938, 141; *ibid.*, 1939, 187; *ibid.*, 1941, 225; (d) Thakor and Shah, *this Journal*, 1946, 23, 199; (e) Parikh and Thakor, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 138.
6. Baker and Lothian, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 626; Rangaswami and Sehadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 7A, 8.
7. (a) Usgaonkar and Jadhav, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 252, 775; (b) *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 346; (c) *Idem*, *ibid.*, 176.
8. Rangaswami and Sehadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 112.
9. (a) Späth and Pfaller, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1212; *ibid.*, 1935, 68, 941; (b) Desai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 5251; (c) Lele and Sethna, *ibid.*, 1958, 23, 1731, Lele, Patel and Sethna, *this Journal* 1960, 37, 775.
10. (a) Dalvi and Sethna, *this Journal*, 1949, 26, 359; (b) Lele, Parikh and Sethna, *ibid.*, 1953, 30, 610; see also Desai and Gaitonde, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 25, 366.
11. (a) Pechmann and Obermiller, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 666; (b) Chakrawarti and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1935, 12, 622; (c) Naik and Jadhav, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 171; see also A. R. Naik, M. Sc., thesis, Bombay University, (1946); (d) Parikh and Shah, *this Journal*, 1942, 19, 395.
12. (a) Merchant and Shah, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 35, 45; (b) *Idem.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 684.
13. (a) Desai and Mavani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 11; (b) *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1947, 25A, 327; (c) Thakor, *Chem. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 234; (d) Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228; Shah and Shah, *ibid.*, 1938, 1427; Dalvi and Shah, *ibid.*, 1939, 1250.

magnitude of— I effect of the corresponding substituent groups or atoms e.g. $-\text{SO}_2\text{H}$, $-\text{NO}_2$ etc. which is in the order of $-\text{SO}_2\text{R}$ $-\text{NO}_2$ $-\text{Br}$ $-\text{COMe}$ etc. as derived from the effect of these substituents on ionisation constants of aliphatic acids¹⁴ and also from the values of substituent inductive constants (σ_i)¹⁵. The— I effect of $-\text{SO}_2\text{H}$ group may be easily judged qualitatively to be greater than that of $-\text{SO}_2\text{R}$ and hence it is greater than that of $-\text{NO}_2$. The +ve character of the corresponding electrophiles then follows the same order.

6-Hydroxycoumarin: In case of this coumarin according to the calculations, the intermediate state leading to substitution in position 5 (state I) is stabilised by 3.84 Kcal of more RE in comparison with that leading to substitution in position 7 (state II) (see table I). The tendency for substitution in position 5 should therefore be greater than that for substitution in position 7. This deduction is in agreement with the experimental observations made in the literature. 6-Hydroxycoumarin and its derivatives are generally less reactive but in the reactions reported such as Fries reaction^{19b}, sulphonation with thionyl chloride¹⁵, and sulphonation with chlorosulphonic acid^{7b}, the substitution has taken place invariably in position 5 and 7-substituted derivative is reported in any one of these reactions. It is interesting to note that these reactions have been reported to be unsuccessful with 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin^{15a,7b}, in which the position 5 is sterically hindered by Me group thus lending support for the greater reactivity of the position 5. The p.m.r. study of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin⁴ gives indirect support to the deduction made above. The values of chemical shifts (-5.50 p.p.m. for the protons at 5 and 7 positions are equal but since the chemical shifts are affected by (i) electron density due to resonance and inductive effects and by (ii) steric effects, it may be easily concluded that the electron² density at position 5 must be more than at 7 since the position 5 is under the steric hindrance of $-\text{Me}$ group in the coumarin molecule. More direct proof would have been obtained if p.m.r. study of 6-hydroxycoumarin was made.

5-Hydroxycoumarin: In case of this coumarin according to the calculations (table I), the resonance energy of the intermediate states leading to substitution in positions 6 and 8 (states I and II respectively) is equal and therefore both the positions should exhibit equal reactivity in electrophilic substitution reactions. The p.m.r. study of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin⁴ amply justify the above deduction. The values of chemical shifts of protons at 6 and 8 positions are nearly equal (-5.18 and -5.20 p.p.m. respectively) showing that both the positions have got nearly the same electron density. Experimental observations made in the literature may be reviewed at this stage. 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives

Fig. 4

14. Jack Hine, "Physical Organic Chemistry" (McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., 1956) p. 68.

15. Taft and Lewis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5343; see also Lloyd Ferguson, "The modern structural theory of Organic Chemistry" (Prentice-Hall, Inc). pp. 418-20,

show greater tendency to get substituted in position 6 in preference to 8 in Friedel and Crafts acylation^{5c}, Fries reaction^{5d}, sulphination with thionyl chloride^{7c} etc. This may be attributed to the stabilisation of the 6-substituted derivative due to metal chelate bond formation with the substituted groups viz. -COMe, -SO₂H etc. (fig. 4) as in these reactions metal salts such as AlCl₃ are used as condensing agents. Such a type of stabilisation is not possible in case of 8-substituted derivative. The sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with chlorosulphonic acid^{12a} to give directly the 6, 8-disulphonic acid of the coumarin derivative is in good agreement with the theoretical deduction but the formation of 8-substituted derivative as major product reported in nitration^{12d} and bromination^{12b} reactions of 5-hydroxycoumarins cannot be well explained. These reactions probably require a more careful investigation.

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